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INGAME
Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation

INGAME

INGAME – Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation – A holistic approach for a cultural shift in education and policy

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National Report: Italy

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1. Introduction

This report is part of the INGAME project (Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation - A holistic approach for a cultural shift in education and policy) funded by the EU and represents one of the specific deliverables of Work Package 2 (Mapping the INGAME Ecosystem of Needs, Practices Target Groups, Stakeholders and Mode of Work).

The project aims at increasing the skills and civic participation of young-adults aged between 18 and 35 using an online game called INGAME. It will allow users to learn from the simulated experience by improving critical thinking on social and political circumstances, building new skills and stimulating interest in collective action.

In Italy, young people aged between 18 and 35 years old are 13.3 million, almost 27% of the total population (Cittalia). Today their active participation in society is not sufficiently reflected in politics and decision-making thus determining a scarce representation of young people instances and needs. One of the objectives of the report is therefore to try to better understand their needs and expectations in order to give young people the opportunity to raise their voice and to increase their role in society.

The first part of the report analyses the current degree of civic participation of young people in Italy, the active policies in the field of civic engagement, gender equality and social inclusion.

The participation of young people takes place mainly through the new digital media; for this reason the analysis intends to investigate the use of the new digital tools in the training and information process with particular reference to *based learning*¹ and the use of *serious games*² as tools to involve and raise awareness among young people.

In the second part of the report the focus is on the results of the research carried out through three online questionnaires addressed to young people aged between 18 and 35 and to the relative main stakeholders (members of youth organizations, NGOs, voluntary associations, etc.). The research

¹ A practice that refers to the use of games to improve the learning experience. The game becomes part of the learning process, and aims to achieve a specific learning outcome, giving students an engaging experience.

² Serious games are digital games that do not have exclusively or primarily an entertainment purpose, but contain educational elements.

should have been based on the implementation of two focus groups, but the COVID emergence for safety reason has led to the decision of carrying on this activity online.

The conclusions show the main evidences that have emerged from the interviews suggestions for the development of the INGAME game.

2. Key findings from Desk Research: the Italian context

2.1 Youth policies and civic engagement

In Italy both the Central State and the Regions, together with the active involvement of the Third Sector and youth organizations, are in charge of the youth policies. At the central level, the Department for Youth Policy and Universal Civil Service of the Presidency of the Council of Ministers is responsible for promoting and linking Government actions aimed at ensuring the implementation of youth policies and manages the Universal Civil Service programme.

The Government, the Regions, the National Association of Italian Municipalities (ANCI) and the Union of Italian Provinces (UPI) contribute to the development of youth legislation, while local authorities, the Third Sector and youth organizations are actively involved in the bottom-up planning and implementation phase.

Every year, the financial resources, the objectives and the priorities for actions and the framework for youth projects are defined through the Unified Conference (CU)³.

The Budget Law of 2019 (Law 145/2018) has established in Italy the National Youth Council, the body in charge of representing young people whose aim is to ensure and increase their participation in civil and political life. The council is committed to recognize and promote the dialogue between youth organizations and institutions, promote active citizenship of young people and support the activities of youth associations.

The theme of youth participation and representation is therefore an important element characterising the policy path for the younger generation.

In the agreement of February 13th, CU-14/2019, one of the approved priorities was precisely "*the promotion of inclusive participation in social and political life, also with a view to enabling young people to participate in the decision-making process*". Following the agreement, the Department for Youth Policy and Universal Civil Service, as the authority responsible for youth policy liaison, signed cooperation agreements with each Region.

³ A legal institute that allows a dialogue on youth policies between the different institutional actors that includes the national Government, the Regions, the Autonomous Provinces, the National Association of Italian Municipalities (ANCI) and the Union of Italian Provinces (UPI).

The Regions are key players in promoting the active participation of young people through the provisions of the various regional laws. Many municipalities have also developed local projects to favour the involvement of young people in the public life of cities.

The Municipality is still the driving force behind the development of the territory according to 90% of young people but also the institution closest to citizens and able to respond more effectively to their needs, compared to the national Government⁴.

New ways of participation

In recent decades, the involvement of young people in traditional civic engagement activities such as voting and political parties affiliation has been steadily decreasing. In the European Union, voting has generally declined, especially between young people aged between 18 and 24, whose turnout is almost 20 percentage points lower than the voting population as a whole (UNICEF 2020).

Also in Italy in recent years there has also been a significant decrease in civic and political participation of young people (Istat, 2017). This situation, however, should not be interpreted as a general lack of interest of young people for politics and social issues, but mainly as a loss of interest and trust in the Italian parties system.

Young people are experimenting with unconventional forms of participation, that are more difficult to measure with traditional analysis tools, but which also allow people with fewer socio-economic resources to influence government choices and amplifying their voice.

The civic commitment of young people takes place mainly through new technologies. There is often a tendency to consider some acts of youth digital participation as simple 'clicktivism', a pejorative term for casual, disposable digital 'activism'. Changing the image of our Facebook profile to support a cause is, of course, very different from voting, participating in a protest or volunteering in the community. However, rather than considering it as a meaningless symbolic act, it is more useful to understand these actions of youth digital civic participation as actions of claiming or expressing one's 'voice', and civic engagement (UNICEF 2020).

There are different ways of civic engagement, for example individual volunteering, electoral engagement, etc. A civilly engaged person has the ability and opportunity to realize about real social change. Internet offers young people precisely this possibility: to engage in voluntary activities, to support campaigns even beyond the borders of their community and country, having the opportunity to create a wider change. One very emblematic example in this sense is the *Friday for Future*

⁴ <https://www.cittalia.it/>

movement that has involved young people from all over the world, who have accumulated the desire to change a situation that involve not only their own community but the whole planet. This movement, together with the *Sardines*⁵ movement in Italy, are examples where online action has joined the offline one. Young people have joined themselves online and then find themselves, close to each other, in the squares and from the squares asking the political decision-makers for a change in the approach to political communication, to the economic agenda, etc.

In Italy the demand for civil participation of young people is high but it is necessary to find the appropriate tools for listening and valorizing it.

⁵ The Sardines Movement, is a phenomenon of Italian political activism, that started in Bologna in November 2019 during the election campaign for the regional elections in Emilia-Romagna Region on January 26th, 2020, declaring itself in opposition to populism and sovereignty that characterize some parties of the Italian right wing.

2.2 Gender discrimination in Italy

According to the **Gender Equality Index**, presented by EIGE (European Institute for Gender Equality), the European agency in charge of monitoring gender equality in Member States, Italy is progressing very fast towards gender equality: in 12 years it has gained almost 14 points, but the results are still lower than the average scores of other European countries in all areas, except health.

The area in which Italy scores lowest is the **access to employment**, where it has even lost a position since 2005.

The **employment rate of women** in Italy is 53% while that of men is 73%. About 33% of women have a part-time contract, compared to 9% of men. On average, women work 33 hours a week while men 40⁶.

These differences have direct impact on the economic system. EIGE notes how inequality in income distribution has increased in Italy. Although the average monthly earnings of women and men have increased, women follow earning 18% less than men. In couples with children, women earn 30% less than men.

The Italian Supreme Court (Corte di Cassazione) has often dealt with the issue of discrimination against women in the workplace and, in its ruling no. 14206 of June 5th 2013, it took the opportunity to strengthen the principle of equality expressed by the law, which expressly forbids workers from being treated differently on the basis of sex, for example, in assigning tasks or awarding qualifications, etc.

Although the legislation provides protection of women's rights as well as men's rights, discrimination continues to exist, rights that are denied even though they are recognised as fundamental. According to young people between 20 and 30 years old, interviewed by Terres des Hommes, **gender equality in Italy is still a distant goal**. Among the major forms of discrimination, 4 out of 10 young people indicated sexual harassment, followed by the lack of recognition of women's skills (for 22% of girls and 17% of boys) and economic discrimination (for 18% of girls and 15% of boys). 16% of boys indicated unpaid domestic work as a major discrimination against women, compared to 6.5% of girls. According to the interviewees, the place where women are most at risk of discrimination is the workplace (for 64% of girls and 42% of boys), followed by the web (which is perceived more dangerous by

⁶ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-equality-index/2019/IT>

males 41% than by females 36%) and politics (for 27% of females compared to 14% of males). But gender stereotypes persist even among the *millennials* themselves. Indeed, according to 46% of boys and 26% of girls, women should put their role as mothers before their professional careers (Terres des Hommes, 2020).

What is needed is to pay more attention on education in order to begin, from an early age, an educational path based on equality and to eliminate stereotypes and so bring about a real cultural change. Law 119/2013 has moved in this direction by introducing an extraordinary **Plan of Action against sexual and gender-based violence**, which provides for the promotion of adequate training of school staff against violence and gender discrimination and for the increase of the awareness, information and training of students in order to prevent episodes of violence against women and gender discrimination.

In addition, Law 107/2015, so called "La Buona Scuola" ensures the implementation of the principles of equal opportunities, promoting in schools of every level, gender equality education, the prevention of gender violence and all discrimination, in order to inform and raise awareness among students, teachers and parents on the issues indicated in Article 5 of Law 119/2013.

Miur (Ministry of Education- Ministry of University and Research) has proposed to support the work of teachers, school staff and families, through the creation of the platform www.noisiamopari.it which brings together teaching materials, projects and initiatives carried out in schools of all levels, collects the experiences of schools on the theme of equal opportunities, information tools, exchange and support.

Women and civic engagement

The gender difference in civic and political participation is an issue to which is still dedicated very low attention, especially considering young adults.

Some researchers have studied the gender gap in participation of teenagers and young adults, identifying a correlation between the family and educational environment and participation: "given the different family and school context of boys and girls, their orientation towards civic and political organizations and participation in civil society activities, strongly depends on the different opportunities that these contexts offer them to become political actors. The family plays a significant role as a 'determinant' of young people's political orientation and civic sense" (Albanesi C. et al., 2014, p. 362).

There are differences in the ways and the tools that boys and girls choose for participating. While the former are more likely to engage in "public" and more traditional forms of political participation (e.g. political party membership), girls are more likely to engage in "private" activism (signing petitions, boycotting products for political reasons and donating money for social/political reasons).

As far as participation in civil society is concerned, 50% of people who are actively involved in voluntary organizations are women; women tend to be more involved in volunteering than men, but occupy leading positions in less than 30% of cases. In Italy, being young and being women represents a major obstacle to access to full citizenship and active participation in civil and political life.

In her their book, Albanesi⁷ underlined the need to increase women's opportunities to emerge as political actors, implementing policies and initiatives that can reduce structural gender inequalities in the labour market and promote equal skills and opportunities in Italian society.

⁷ Albanesi C., Zani B., Cicognani E. (2014). *Youth civic and political participation through the lens of gender: The Italian case*. Human Affairs.

2.3 Social Inclusion

National policies for social inclusion are characterised by a range of initiatives and tasks differentiated by scope of intervention and type of instruments.

Specifically, some of the national policies, with particular regard to active inclusion interventions, support directly the incomes of individuals and families; another line of action is dedicated, instead, to the quantitative and qualitative analysis of emerging phenomena of poverty, the study of extreme poverty conditions and the definition of the appropriate methods of intervention.

Poverty is a complex phenomenon that depends on many factors. It is not only linked to a lack of income but is also closely linked to access to opportunities and therefore the possibility of participating to the economic and social life of the country. The worsening of economic and social inequalities contribute to a reduction in the degree of citizens' participation in democratic life and to the strengthening of distrust of public institutions.

In 2018 in Italy, according to the National Statistics Institute (ISTAT), the population at risk of poverty or social exclusion is 27,3 %⁸ (pre-covid-19 data) that is quite higher than the European for the same period (21.7 %). (Istat, 2020, p. 42)

Among the most vulnerable groups at risk of exclusion there are young people aged between 18 and 35. From 2017 to 2018, the incidence of absolute poverty in this age group, increased by 8%, and has more than quadrupled since the pre-crisis years.

Young Italians are facing with an unequal, immobile labour market, characterized by a strong job insecurity. The absence of qualified work positions and career progression prospects are unfortunately a negative feature of the National production system, characterized by a peculiar fragmentation and a strong underutilization of human capital.

The first data on the economic consequences of the covid 19 emergency reveal that young people are the most affected. They often have temporary contracts or precarious and undeclared work and are more likely to be fired first or to suffer reductions in working hours. They generally work in the sectors, such as retail and hospitality (including tourism-related sectors), that are most affected by virus containment measures, such as lock-down and travel bans.

Eurostat reveal that in April 2020, the youth unemployment rate was 15.4 % in the EU and 15.8 % in the euro area, up from 14.6 % and 15.1 % respectively in the previous month. Compared with March 2020, youth unemployment increased by 159 000 in the EU and by 89 000 in the euro area⁹.

⁸ <https://www.istat.it/storage/rapporti-tematici/sdgs/2020/goal1.pdf>

⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Unemployment_statistics#Youth_unemployment

In Italy, 5.5% of young people declared they lost their jobs permanently and 30% temporarily, values only slightly higher than the general population, respectively 4.7% and 29%. On average in Europe, 16% of young people interviewed also said they are afraid of losing their job in the following three months, with a slightly higher value in Italy, with a percentage equal to 18.1% of the youth population (Mascherini M., 2020).

In this context, the aspirations of young Italians to a fairer future seem even more compromised today.

The Neet phenomenon

A sign of the difficulties experienced by the youngest people in Italy is represented by the high number of NEET (Not in Education, Employment or Training), young people who do not have or search an employment, do not study and are not engaged in training or professional updating activities.

The Ministry of Labour and Social Policies manages the National Operational Programme (NOP) Youth Employment Initiative, through which the Youth Guarantee initiative is implemented in Italy.

The Youth Guarantee is the European Plan for the fight against youth unemployment aimed at encouraging the implementation of guidance, education and training and job placement measures, in support of young people who are not engaged in a working activity, nor included in a school or training course (Neet- Not in Education, Employment or Training).

In 2018 almost 1 out of 4 young Italians between 15 and 34 years of age were in such condition, with an incidence of NEETs almost 4 percentage points higher than in 2005 (Maslennikov M., 2019). Two million young people forced into the limbo of eternal children, condemned to an unfinished life project, stuck in the construction of their adult identity, suspended in a limbo that generates distrust in the institutions and deterioration of the sense of social belonging.

Percentage of NEETs in EU countries among the population aged 20-34. Year 2018. Source: Eurostat

The main factors that involve a risk for young people to become NEET are (Agostini C., Sacconi T., 2020, p. 34):

- a disability;
- the female gender;
- an immigration background;
- a low level of education;
- residence in remote areas;
- low family income;
- a family context characterised by unemployment;
- a family context characterised by divorce experiences.

If we look at the dimensions of gender and nationality, we see that in Italy, the number of NEETs is higher among girls and young people of foreign origin (16%). (Agostini C., Sacconi T., 2020, p. 37-38)

% young people who do not study and do not work, because of characteristics

Source: <https://www.infodata.ilsole24ore.com/2019/07/31/numero-giovani-non-studia-ne-lavora-cresce-specie-fra-le-ragazze/>

% NEET per gender

Source: <https://www.infodata.ilsole24ore.com/2019/07/31/numero-giovani-non-studia-ne-lavora-cresce-specie-fra-le-ragazze/>

Therefore, there are many difficulties that young people have to face and to do so effective interventions are needed, aimed at ensuring that the younger generations are not left behind and can be valorized as resources for the Country (Maslennikov M., 2019).

2.4 Game based learning and serious games

Since 2015, Italy has adopted Law 107/2015, which encourages the use of new technologies to increase students' skills, but the use of digital resources in school practice is not yet widespread.

During the Covid emergency, however, the use of e-learning, in part, has guaranteed the continuation of teaching activities, has helped children to maintain contact with their pre-covid normality, reducing the sense of isolation and the exacerbation of inequalities. New technologies have become fundamental as well as the search for innovative and engaging methods and tools.

Since 2015 **Italy** has adopted Law 107/2015, which encourages the use of new technologies to increase students' skills, but the use of digital resources in school practice is not yet widespread. The recent health crisis and the need to develop distance learning have highlighted the need to develop innovative initiatives, using new technologies as a tool for training and inclusion.

Currently, one of the most advanced tools in the training scenario is represented by serious games, which are able to combine the game with educational elements. Their purpose is to share, in a playful context, an effective and pleasant training experience in which the user, and his choices, are at the heart of the game.

One example is **Maggie. The treasure of Sehat**¹⁰. The game was created to tackle important mathematical issues. Maggie is not a scientist and to continue the adventure she must acquire specific scientific skills. In this way the most important concepts are presented in a non-invasive way, becoming an engaging part of the story without distorting it. Playing boys and girls in the role of a nice, adventurous, curious, brave, determined problem-solver, at ease with logical mathematical thinking, capable of achieving successful goals is a transversal way to propose a different model of femininity.

Applying serious games to teaching, means changing the teaching methodology, including learning based on group activities and the achievement of objectives through scores and awards (Save the Children, 2020). Moreover, learning based on games allows to keep students' attention high and to stimulate them to problem solving.

¹⁰ <https://www.soroptimist.it/maggie/>

Video Games and civic engagement

Digital games allow you to immerse yourself in scenarios and settings that are difficult to represent in reality and in so doing to put yourself "in the shoes of others", to be the protagonists. Precisely this immersive dimension makes these games suitable to convey social messages, to raise people's awareness of issues such as bullying, immigration, gender discrimination. Video games and in particular serious games offer a new way to convey the concepts of integration and inclusion, educating people to comprehension and diversity.

Despite the fact that serious games are not yet widespread, in Italy there are many companies dedicated to the creation of these products. In 2017 in Rome took place LET'S PLAY, the first video game festival. An event during which video games operators, fans of the sector and institutions discussed the economic future of the sector and all the possible uses of these tools in the cultural, social, educational, health and sports fields. The theme that opened the event was "'Serious Games and migrants. The video game as a bridge between peoples and cultures". It allowed to realize that serious games can be useful to deal with delicate issues such as immigration in Italy, they can help, for example, young Italians to understand the conditions of some immigrants by putting themselves in the shoes of an unaccompanied foreign minor or helping a young migrant to find their way in the Italian reception system.

"Making people experience diversity, especially if it is an unpleasant condition, can be more effective because it can give more interesting cues for its understanding than simply documenting the existence of the Other" (Prosperi V., 2011, p. 156).

A report by the Pew Internet & American Life Project found that young people who engage in this "civic" gaming experience are more frequently engaged in supporting social causes both online and offline: they explore the issues covered by the game, support election campaigns, participate in fundraising and volunteer activities.

As Joseph Kahne, director of the Civic Engagement Research Group at Mills College, said, "games that simulate aspects of civic and political life have the ability to promote players' civic skills and engagement. Parents, teachers and all those who work with young people should be aware of the great diversity of video games- so that they can take full advantage of games and their civic potential" (PND, 2008).

3. Good Practices

In Italy, the use of serious games is increasing especially in the private sector. Companies are increasingly using video games to create training experiences for their employees and to retain or acquire new customers.

However, in recent years, there has been an increase in the number of projects promoted by NGOs, schools and institutions that use online games to convey social messages, to raise awareness of current issues in the Italian public debate, such as immigration, and to increase the participation of young people in the political and social life of the Country.

There are not many examples of games aimed at the target audience of the INGAME project, especially if we look at the theme of gender equality.

Below we will describe and analyse two examples of online games that can be a useful starting point for the development of INGAME.

The first is "**Nei miei Panni**" is a video game that challenges the participant to live a month as a foreigner. The game has been developed by UNAR (National Office for Racial Discrimination), the office appointed by the State to guarantee the right to equal treatment of all people, regardless of their ethnic or racial origin, age, religious belief, sexual orientation, gender identity or the fact that they are people with disabilities.

<http://www.unar.it/NeiMieiPanni/italiano/index.html>

The game puts the player in front of the daily choices that each individual makes, regardless of his or her nationality: moving house, buying a car, choosing a school for their children, etc., but making us notice the differences, making us understand what extra difficulties a foreigner or a person of foreign origin, has to face in Italy.

To win, two parameters must be taken into account: the starting economic budget and the happiness points. In fact, the compromise lies in understanding how much we are willing to give up our happiness, dignity and respect to achieve the goal. If even one of the two criteria falls below zero, we lose.

Within the game a lot of information, real data, statistics are provided to enable the player to make the right decision and to spread as much important and updated data about the world of immigration in Italy as possible.

The interesting aspect of this game that can be used as a food for thought in the development of INGAME is the use of two elements:

- the score corresponding to the player's response, which prompts him or her to think more about his or her choice and then try both to empathize with the character and to inquire.
- the data and information provided. Once the player has made his decision, the game provides a look at the real situation in the country using data from official sources.

Another game that can be a valid starting point for the development of INGAME is **EmpoweringYou**, developed within the Erasmus+ European Programme, by six organizations including the Italian CSV MARCHE- Centro Servizi per il volontariato delle Marche (<http://empoweringyouproject.eu/en/>).

The game is aimed at young people between 13 and 30 years old, at risk of social exclusion, with the aim of promoting their civic and democratic participation.

The game can be accessed after registering to the platform, either via PC or mobile.

The game shows debates between two or more characters on different topics such as: waste management, climate change, migration, disability, young people voting, volunteering. What is covered less and the theme of gender equality.

There is no real identification with the characters, but through the questions present during the scenes, young players can understand the ways in which they exercise their civic engagement and participation. Through the game you can access documents and articles to deepen the topics covered and, from the platform, download a guide to the use of the game for teachers and trainers.

4. Key findings from Field Research: need assessment

This chapter provides the results of the answers of three online questionnaires, via google form, in completely anonymous form.

The aim of the interviews was to investigate the degree of civic participation of young people, their needs and the knowledge of young people and stakeholders of the existence of video games applied to civic engagement, gender equality and social inclusion.

Stakeholders were also asked to explain the difficulties faced in involving young people in civic engagement activities and the factors influencing their participation.

The first questionnaire (Q1) answered by six young people, three girls and three boys, most of them (66.7%) between 31 and 35 years old, all involved in training and study activities.

The second questionnaire (Q2) addressed to project stakeholders. 10 people answered members of youth organizations (4), civil society organizations (2), international organizations (2), social promotion associations (1) and a freelancer.

The third questionnaire (Q3) answered by 30 young people aged between 18 and 35, 13 women and 17 men¹¹.

What emerged strongly from the three questionnaires is the need for young people to feel an active part of the change. Not only to be the target of youth policy, but also taking part in all the processes of building interventions. Many young people feel that they are not considered seriously by adults, in general as citizens but also from a political point of view.

This widespread belief reduces young people's belief in their ability to have civic and political influence, and is an important disincentive to involvement and participation. What drives young people towards civic engagement is the possibility to feel that they are the protagonists of change.

The responses of the young people revealed what had already been found in the desk-based research: for only three young people out of 36, civic commitment coincides with political participation and voting. For the most part, civic commitment means the *common good, attention to others people and to the environment*. 24 out of 30 young people participated in initiatives and campaigns of social interest both online and offline. The most widely used form of participation by respondents is the

¹¹ For further details of the questionnaires, see annexes.

online petition (9) and the topic on which young people have been most active is the environment (13). Among the successful initiatives for civic involvement of young people, the Friday for future movement was mentioned several times.

Figure 1 – Results from questionnaire – Q 3

According to the interviewees, the involvement of young people must move from combining online and offline initiatives. *"Activities that could increase youth involvement are those that combine the digital aspects of social media with participation in offline training and awareness raising events, cultural and sports activities with a focus on social inclusion and social sensitivity. Activities in which young people themselves are the protagonists. It would be important to develop these activities as early as the last years of high school so that young adults are better prepared and prepared to participate in public life in their own country"*.

Among the best practices to increase the civic participation of young people, the stakeholders indicated the projects: Europe Goes Local, which tends to localize youth policies, and the recognition of the Youth Worker as a key player; Europiamo, which aims to bring the new generations closer to European opportunities, promotes the participation of young people in civil society and shares good practices among those involved; Mode United Nation, simulation of the work of the United Nations in which the role of ambassadors is played by students.

When asked about knowledge of examples of video games for educational or awareness-raising purposes, only a few respondents answered positively. Among the examples cited by young people

there are: Minecraft education edition, business games and platforms used for foreign language learning.

Gamification is considered a tool to improve critical reflection on the social and political situation of young adults: "*video games can be used to disseminate useful concepts to improve the social situation*". What is valued is the possibility offered by video games to put themselves in each other's shoes, to empathize.

The knowledge of serious games is still partial, but the interviewees showed interest and desire to discover this world and the opportunities it offers.

5. Conclusions

As we have seen, the decline in civic participation of young people is linked to a lack of confidence in traditional models of participation, to the need of the new generations to feel an active part of change and not merely a target of youth policy. In order to understand the real level of civic engagement of young people it cannot fail to consider the new forms of participation conveyed by the new digital media.

Also in the educational field, new technologies are offering new opportunities, especially in light of the recent health emergency and the need to develop distance learning.

In this context, serious games represent an innovative tool that manages to combine training/information and entertainment. Moreover, thanks to their ability to make the user the protagonist of the story, they are excellent tools to make young people aware of social issues such as gender discrimination and social exclusion.

To young people and stakeholders interviewed have also asked which characteristics a game like INGAME should have. The game, while dealing with serious topics, should maintain its playful aspect; it should simulate situations and circumstances very similar to reality, stimulate further reflections and propose in-depth analysis, depending on the game choices. Through a scoring system, the game should challenge the user to act not only in the virtual world, but also in reality. The game should also be accessible from mobile and be connected to a forum where participants can confront each other on the issues addressed.

From the analysis of the good practices identified, it has also emerged that characteristics to be exploited are, the possibility to put oneself in the other's shoes, the deepening of the themes through the reference to informative material and official data, and the presence of a guide to help teachers and trainers to use the game for educational purposes.

What emerged from the analysis is a relative gap in the number of games dealing with gender equality for young people aged 18-35.

Stimulating the civic participation of young people through new technologies does not mean closing themselves in a digital world, but allowing them to have all the tools and information to go and act on the surrounding reality and bringing the change they so much need and are able to contribute to create.

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7. Annexes

7.1 Annex 1: Questionnaire 1- Evaluation grid

Evaluation grid: questionnaire 1 (target group)		
Partner		
Age profile of the participants (<i>please insert the number of people belonging to each age / age group</i>)	__1__ 18-20 ____ 21-25	
	__1__ 26-30 __4__ 31-35	
Number of participants and their gender split	Females: 3	Males: 3
In minimum 2 pages and maximum 4 pages:		
Question n°	Common theme	Contrasting findings
5. What does civic engagement mean to you?	Civic commitment is one of the possibilities that each of us has to pursue a path of social justice. Making oneself available to the community. (5)	Vote. Participate actively in political life (1).
6. What kind of activities do you think should be delivered to increase the participation of young adult in public life in general and more specifically, their civic engagement?	Sensitization activities, training meetings, proposals for operational activities (learning by doing). Involve young people through the use of social media to be combined with socializing initiatives and live activities (5).	Organize meetings during the last years of high school so that young people can participate in public life (1).
7. Do you know any policies, practices and interventions for promoting young civic engagement, social inclusion and gender equality? If so, should they improve or change?	-Performing activities in schools/universities - Performing playful-cultural activities - Young people also protagonists, not only helpers! Young people must have roles of responsibility, be part of the whole process. They must have the possibility to propose new ideas.	no

<p>8. Are you aware of new technologies (digital tools and mobile devices like GPS, PDAs, Tablet PCs, Virtual Reality, handheld technologies, mobile learning technologies, etc.) and innovative approaches (like for example Online Gaming, Serious Games, Game-based Learning) that can be used to discuss global issues, like social inclusion and gender equality? If yes, have you ever used them and why?</p>	<p>5 out of 6 people don't know about it.</p>	
<p>9. We are developing an online game, called INGAME which will allow users to learn from simulated experience enhancing critical reflection on social and political circumstances, build skills and stimulate interest for collective action. What would an online game like INGAME need to attract your interest? Which features would you like the game to have?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The game should be fun. - It should be an opportunity to come face to face with a problem or ethical question and experience one's own behaviour, choices and perspective. 	

7.2 Questionnaire 2: Evaluation grid

Evaluation grid: questionnaire 2 (stakeholders)

Evaluation grid: questionnaire 2 (stakeholders)		
Partner		
Age profile of the participants <i>(please insert the number of people belonging to each age / age group)</i>	19-25 years __5__ 36-45 years _4__ Above 55 years ____	26-35 years _1__ 46-55 years ____
Number of participants and their gender split	Females: 8	Males: 2
In minimum 2 pages and maximum 4 pages:		
Question n°	Common theme	Contrasting findings
4. Which factors influence the civic engagement of young adult?	- Sense of belonging to one's own culture and community (4) -Interest in the issue addressed (4)	-Time. Lack of information. Political representatives who are not examples of concreteness. -Family environment -The chance to help others and learn at the same time
5. What kind of activities do you think should be delivered to increase the participation of young adult in public life in general and more specifically, their civic engagement?	-Information and training courses -Activities that are of interest to them -Voluntary activities	
6. What are the main difficulties you face in involving young people in civic engagement activities	Confidence in adults, in themselves and above all in the possibility of being able to change things. Lack of interest. Difficulty in creating entertainment and motivation on an ongoing basis.	The fact that they are not paid.

<p>7. In your area of work, do you know of successful initiatives aimed to improve civic participation of young people and their attention to social inclusion or gender equality issues? If so, which are the main elements of success?</p>	<p>Yes, the main element of success is the active involvement in the first person, the feeling of being part of something bigger in a well-organized and structured group.</p>	
<p>8. Are you aware of new technologies (digital tools and mobile devices, Virtual Reality, hand-held technologies, mobile learning technologies, etc.) and innovative approaches (like for example Online Gaming, Serious Games, Game-based Learning) that can be used to discuss global issues, like social inclusion and gender equality?</p>	<p>6 people say they are not familiar with this type of technology, but they are interested in it and believe it can be useful. Three people know these tools and one of them used them for educational purposes.</p>	
<p>9. We are developing an online game, called INGAME which will allow users to learn from simulated experience enhancing critical reflection on social and political circumstances, build skills and stimulate interest for collective action. What would an online game like INGAME need to attract young interest? Which features would you like the game to have?</p>	<p>Rapidity, award ceremony, a narrative/story, playable also on the smartphone while on the metro or bus, obviously fun Interactive and engaging. That it simulates reality well.</p>	<p>Accessible to everybody</p>

7.3 Questionnaire 3 – Evaluation grid

Evaluation grid: questionnaire 3 (target group)

Evaluation grid: questionnaire 3 (target group)		
Partner		
Age profile of the participants <i>(please insert the number of people belonging to each age / age group)</i>	_9__ 18-20 _5__ 21-25 _12__ 26-30 _4__ 31-35	
Number of participants in and their gender split	Females: 13 Males: 17	
In minimum 2 pages and maximum 4 pages:		
Question n°	Common theme	Contrasting findings
5. What does civic engagement mean to you?	Commitment to others Have respect for your city and citizens, and participate politically and culturally. Participation in social life.	For me it is enough not to be a burden, so it is trivial to have a job/study to have a training that leads to a job. So do not be a burden on society as for example those who take advantage of citizenship income or pensions of various kinds.
6. Have you participated in any of these initiatives in the last two years?	Awareness campaigns on social networks (4) Demonstrations of square, marches, sit-in (8) Petitions (10) None of these (6)	Volunteering (1) All options (1)
7. What was the cause?	Environment (13) Human rights and migration (3) Freedom of the press (2)	No cuts in health and education, more security for workers and entertainment workers, Kurdistan (1). Feminist cause (1)

<p>8. Do you think that technology could play a role in promoting social inclusion and equal participation? If yes, how? If not, why not?</p>	<p>Yes, in thousands of different ways, technology opens doors we haven't yet been able to imagine. Yes. Social networks are an emblematic example yes because through technology you can reach more people.</p>	<p>Technology is at the same time the most inclusive and exclusive (in the sense of exclusion) tool, as there is the possibility of connecting people with similar interests in an instantaneous way, even if they are at opposite poles of the world. At the same time, however, it can be a means of total social exclusion in 2 different ways: either you create an alternative reality in which to live or you are excluded from others. In conclusion, technology can be the means with more power of inclusion if used with common sense.</p>
<p>9. Are you aware of game-based learning initiatives? If so, could you name these? what do you think?</p>	<p>NO (23) <i>No, but I think it's a great idea to make the learner more involved and involved.</i> Yes (7): games for children, to learn languages, minecraft education, minecraft uncensored library</p>	
<p>10. Do you know of any initiatives on young people's civic engagement you consider 'best practices'? If yes, name them.</p>	<p>No (16) Yes (14): volunteering (5); Initiatives and training in schools (2); Friday for future (2); National Civil Service (2).</p>	<p>The Sardine movement (1)</p>
<p>11. How do you think Gamification could be used to enhance critical reflection on social and political circumstances of young adult?</p>	<p>I don't know (8) Yes, Gamification can be used to improve critical reflection on the social and political situation of young adults: <i>it can be used to show the specific situation you want to treat from a different and more engaging point of view.</i></p>	<p>I think gamification can lighten everyone's life and make it more enjoyable and varied. Video games can be used to spread useful concepts to improve the social situation. It can be used to show the specific situation you want to treat from a different and more engaging point of view.</p>

<p>12. According to you what are the most successful activities and practices for fostering civic participation, social inclusion and gender equality among young people (i.e. diversity-days with games, workshops, exhibitions, theatre, round-tables/debates, competitions on drawings, photographs, etc.)?</p>	<p>Cultural or social events, debates or organization of events. civic training at school and using several means (television, internet)</p>	<p>Do something without technology. Compulsory civilian service I think a movie or TV series</p>
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